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THE PROBLEM OF FETAL GROWTH RETRACTION SYNDROME IN OBSTETRICS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....10

THERAPY

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CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA.....22
3. **Boltaev J. Kamol, Rizaeva J. Malika**
THE ROLE OF PREDICTORS IN THE FORMATION OF THROMBOSIS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION (REVIEW ARTICLE).....27
4. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Akhmedova A. Gulchekhra**
THE ROLE OF ANTIFILAGGRIN ANTIBODIES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AT AN EARLY STAGE.....33
5. **Akhmedova Sh. Nilufar, Rizayeva J. Malika**
CHANGES IN ANTITHROMBIN INDICATORS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION.....39
6. **Agababyan R. Irina, Djabbarova M. Nafisa**
CURRENT ISSUES IN MODERN TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....44
7. **Abdushukurova R. Komila, Akhmedov A. Ibrat**
FOUNDATIONS OF IMMUNOPATHOGENESIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....55
8. **Makhatmuradova N.Nargiza**
FEATURES OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN NONSPECIFIC INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA.....66
9. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Eshmuratov E. Sardor**
FEATURES OF THE SUBPOPULATION COMPOSITION OF PERIPHERAL BLOOD LYMPHOCYTES IN THE FIRST PERIODS OF THE DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....73
10. **Kityan S.Aleksandr**
COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....78

SURGERY

11. **Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arziev A Ismoil, Arzieva B Gulnora**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....83
12. **Zohidova H Sanoat, Mamataliyev R. Abdumalik**
DESPITE THE COMPLEXITY AND SERIOUSNESS OF THE DISEASE, MODERN TREATMENT METHODS CAN ACHIEVE POSITIVE RESULTS AND IMPROVE THE PROGNOSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....91
13. **Achilov T. Mirzakarim, Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Mirmuxammedov Dj.Nasimjon, Shakulov M. Azizbek**
INTRAGENATION OF PROLOSED RECTUM (CASE FROM PRACTICE).....97

14. **Babajanov S. Akhmadjon, Akhmedov I. Adkham, Shamsiev J. Shokhzod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE INTRAOPERATIVE THYROMETRY METHOD IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BENIGN THYROID GLAND PATHOLOGIES.....104
15. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
USE OF TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF STARGED ANTERIOR HERNIA ABDOMINAL WALL (LITERATURE REVIEW).....113
16. **Avazov A. Abdurakhim., Shakirov M. Bobur., Hakimov A. Erkin**
TREATMENT OF ISOLATED BURNS OF THE HAND AND FOOT IN A HUMID ENVIRONMENT WITH SILVER-CONTAINING PREPARATIONS.....120

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

17. **Fozilov A. Uktam**
DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS USING A COMPUTER PROGRAM.....126
18. **Nurova N. Shoxsanam**
THE INCIDENCE OF CHRONIC DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE WITH BREAST CANCER.....136
19. **Ibragimova Kh. Malika, Ruzikulova Sh. Munira**
PERIODONTAL STATUS ACCORDING TO THE CPITN INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH FATTY HEPATOSIS.....141
20. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Rakhimov Kh. Jahongir.**
INFLUENCE OF MAGNETOTHERAPY ON VARIOUS SYSTEMS OF THE BODY AND ON THE PROCESS OF WOUND HEALING IN CHILDREN WITH CLEFT LIP.....149
21. **Gaffarov A. Sunnatullo, Astanov M. Otabek**
DENTAL CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHIATRIC PATHOLOGIES.....154
22. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Mamedova Sh. Nigina**
EVALUATION OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF ODONTOGENIC PURULENT INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE JAWS.....161
23. **Agababyan R. Irina, Ismoilov M. Rajabboy**
SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN ATHEROSCLEROSIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS.....166
24. **Boymuradov A. Shukhrat, Ruzibayev R. Dilshod**
RESULTS OF ELIMINATING OF PERFORATION OF THE MAXILLARY SINUS BOTTOM USING PRF.....173
25. **Abasniya R. Surayyo**
LABORATORY INDICATORS OF IMPROVING METHODS OF TREATING PERIODONTITIS AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM REGION.....182
26. **Eronov Q. Yoqub**
THE INFLUENCE OF PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE MICROBIOCENOSIS OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES ON ORAL HYGIENE IN CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES.....187

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

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CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ACOUSTIC REFLEX OF THE INTRA-EAR MUSCLES IN OCCUPATIONAL HEARING DISORDERS.....193

28. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF
CHRONIC INFLAMMATION OF THE MIDDLE EAR.....200
29. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Ne`matov S. O`ktam, Khamraev Kh. Farid**
LOBULAR CAPILLARY HAEMANGIOMA OF THE NASAL CAVITY DURING
PREGNANCY: A CLINICAL CASE.....209
30. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Dustboboyev S. Dilshod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SURGICAL APPROACH FOR CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE
MAXILLARY SINUS.....214

PEDIATRICS

31. **Rakhmatullaev A. Akmal, Terebaev A. Bilim, Mazhidov Kh. Temur**
MODERN VIEWS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT PAYRE'S SYNDROME IN
CHILDREN.....221
32. **Garifulina M. Lilya M., Goyibova S. Nargiza**
MICROALBUMINURIA AS AN INDICATOR OF METABOLIC DISORDERS IN
OBESITY CHILDREN.....227
33. **Yusupova U. Umida**
PECULIARITIES OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN EARLY CHILDREN WITH NON-SOCIAL
PNEUMONIA LIVING IN ECOLOGICAL REGIONS.....233
34. **Kuryazova M. Sharofat, Khudaynazarova R. Salomat**
FREQUENCY AND STRUCTURE OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY IN
CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS.....241

CHILDREN SURGERY

35. **Yuldashev A. Botir, Murodova D. Malika**
ASSESSMENT OF CARDIORENAL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE
NEPHRITIC SYNDROME.....247

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

36. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Khakimova Z. Sohuba**
BRAIN REGENERATION: STEM CELL THERAPY FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE
DISEASES.....255
37. **Kodirov A. Umid, Abdurakhimov Mukhiddin**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CHRONIC BRUCELLIOSIS.....262
38. **Kodirov A. Umid, Turdiev Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CASE OF HERPETIC INFECTION.....269
39. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN PATIENTS
WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME.....275
40. **Muminov A. Bekzod, Matmurodov J. Rustambek, Khalimova M. Khanifa, Nazarova F. Madinabonu, Umirova M. Surayyo.**
CHANGED LEVELS OF INTERLEUKIN-6 IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS
WITH COVID-19.....281
41. **Mirjuraev M. Elbek, Samiev S. Asliddin, Urakov U. Shokir**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH
COGNITIVE CHANGES IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL CIRCULATION DISEASES.....289

ONCOLOGY AND GEMATOLOGY

42. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Yusupbekov A. Abrorjon, Tuychiyev D. Otabek**
STUDY OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STAGES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE IN THE
EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTRIC CANCER.....296
43. **Abdiyev Kattabek Makhmatovich**
COMPLICATIONS OF PRIMARY MYELOFIBROSIS AND TACTICS OF THEIR
TREATMENT.....303
44. **Azimova A. Makhbuba, Nasirova K. Khurshedakhon**
THYROID DYSFUNCTION IN BREAST CANCER.....316

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

45. **Kamalova A. Yokutkhon, Sulaimonov Sh. Vakil**
FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF THERAPEUTIC PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN
PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....325

MORPHOLOGY

46. **Kuryazov K. Akbar, Olimov Sh. Siddik**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN ORTHOPEDIC STATUS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE
AGE.....331
47. **Khoshimov L. Bobur, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE AORTA IN EXPERIMENTAL METABOLIC
SYNDROME.....339
48. **Muzaffarova Sh. Nargiza, Sheryigitova I. Nigina, Azizov M. Mardon**
A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE HUMAN BODY.....346
49. **Abdusattarov A. Adahamjon Alisherovich, Juraeva A. Mohigul, Ashuralieva A. Mavlyuda.**
THE CONCEPT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....353
50. **Oripov S. Firdavs Suratovich, Eshkabilova T. Surayo**
IMPACT OF ENERGY DRINKS COMPONENTS ON THE HUMAN BODY AND ITS
COMPLICATIONS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....361
51. **RADJABOV B. Akhtam**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL
DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC
ALCOHOLISM.....368
52. **TILYABOV Ikram, USMANOV Ravshan**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED
BY STREPTOZOTOCIN.....373

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

53. **Tilyakov B. Aziz, Tilyakov A. Xasan, Ayozboev A. Zuhridin, Nabiye A. Muhammadi**
CRITERIA FOR THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF COMBINED
CHEST INJURIES IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE.....383
54. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Nomozov N. Fazliddin**
OPTIMAL METHODS OF CARE FOR VICTIMS WITH COMBINED BONE AND
VASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....390
55. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Tilyakov A. Khasan**
ASSESSMENT OF X-RAY INDICATORS OF INSTABILITY OF THE DISTAL
RADIOULNARY JOINT IN CHILDREN.....401

56. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek**
 DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (SCIENTIFIC
 REVIEW).....408

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

57. **Iskandarov I. Alisher, Kaidarov A. Makhammadali**
 EXPERT ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATION CONTENT OF CLINICAL AND
 MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS DURING THERMAL EXPOSURE ETHYLENE
 GLYCOL.....414
58. **Turonov Bobur Sobir ugli, Iskandarov Alisher Iskandarovitch**
 VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF
 IRIDOLOGY.....420
59. **Davranova E. Aziza, Toshmamatov Sh. Alimardon, Tashev Sh. Ulmas, Ganiev N. Sobirzhon, Kushbakov M. Akbar**
 FORENSIC CHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS.....425

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

60. **Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza, Yakubova S. Nigina, Mirzaeva U. Adolat**
 CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH TICK-
 BORNE RICKETSIOSIS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....434
61. **Achilova M. Matlyuba, Shodiyeva A. Dilafruz**
 ASSESSMENT OF THE SAFETY OF HIGHLY ACTIVE ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY
 IN PATIENTS WITH HIV INFECTION.....448
62. **Imamova A. Ilmira**
 RELEVANCE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS.....453
63. **Allaberganova S. Zumrad, Karimova A. Maqsuda, Rajapov Y. Shahzod, Kurbanbaeva K. Dilnoza**
 STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND PROTEOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF YEAST-LIKE
 FUNGI OF THE GENUS CANDIDA.....461
64. **Oslanov A. Absamat, Kodirov F. Jonibek, Samibaeva Kh. Umida, Suyarov A. Ulugbek, Qozieva L. Dilobar, Djumanazarov N. Sardorbek, Boysunov Ch. Shokhzod**
 SOME ASPECTS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MEASLES IN CHILDREN UNDER
 ONE YEAR OF ONE YEAR.....467

OPHTHALMOLOGY

65. **Yusupov F. Azamat, Khusanbaev Sh. Khasanjon, Abdullaeva I. Saida.**
 COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR SOLUTION.....475
66. **Xamidullayev F. Firdavs. Normatova M. Nargiza Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin**
 EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF BROLUCIZUMAB IN TREATING DIABETIC
 MACULAR EDEMA.....482
67. **Karimova Kh. Muyassar, Ubaydullaev O. Sardor**
 CLINICAL CASE OF IOL IMPLANTATION IN POSTVITRECTOMY EYE WITH
 APHAKIA.....491

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OPTIMAL METHODS OF CARE FOR VICTIMS WITH COMBINED BONE AND VASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES

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ANNOTATION

Objective. To improve the results of treatment of patients with open and closed combined bone and vascular injuries of the lower limbs.

Material and Methods. We conducted an analysis of data from 151 patients with open and closed combined bone and vascular injuries of the lower extremities. There were 113 (74%) adult males, 30 (19.9%) females, and 15 (9.9%) children of both sexes under 18 years of age. 127 (84.1%) patients were delivered in the first 1-6 h after the injury, some of the victims - 7 (4.6%) - within 6-24 h, 17 (11.3%) - later than 1 day after the injury. 52 (34.4%) patients were delivered independently, 55 (36.4%) - by ambulance, 44 (29.1%) - by transfer from other clinics.

Results. Of the total number of reconstructive surgeries performed (n=137), segments were preserved in 129 (94.2%) and reamputation was performed in 8 (5.8%).

Conclusions. Thus, in case of segmental circulatory disorders the most optimal approach is the preliminary fixation (with spokes or pins) of the bone fragments necessary for revascularization with the subsequent immobilization of the limb with external fixation devices after wound closure.

Key words: bone-vascular injuries, complete and incomplete amputations, osteosynthesis, arterial anastomoses, autovenous prosthesi

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ОПТИМАЛЬНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОКАЗАНИЯ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ ПОСТРАДАВШИМ С СОЧЕТАННЫМИ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ КОСТЕЙ И СОСУДОВ НИЖНИХ КОНЕЧНОСТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Следует отметить, что проблема лечения открытых и закрытых переломов нижних конечностей в сочетании с повреждением крупных кровеносных сосудов в настоящее время стоит достаточно остро. Основными причинами таких травм в основном являются дорожно-транспортные происшествия, спортивные травмы и травмы, связанные с производством. Повреждение сосудов при переломах костей наблюдается в 0,6-10% случаев, что в среднем составляет 4-5% [5, 111; 8, 58-63; 10, 308-325].

В настоящее время, благодаря стремительному развитию ангио- и микрохирургии, ранней своевременной диагностике (пульсоксиметрия, ультразвуковая доплерография, МСКТ-ангиография и др.) и, как следствие, своевременному проведению реконструктивных операций, частота ампутаций значительно снизилась. Однако, несмотря на достигнутые успехи, по-прежнему существует высокая частота ампутаций (3-60%) и смертельных исходов (7.3-24.0%) [2, 22-25; 7, 1011]. Например, в случаях не прямой травмы перелом бедренной кости в нижней трети сопровождается повреждением артерии в 11% случаев, вывихом большеберцовой кости в 8% случаев и внутрисуставным переломом бедра.

Ключевые слова: костно-сосудистые повреждения, полные и неполные ампутации, остеосинтез, артериальные анастомозы, аутовенозные протезы.

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ОУОҚ СУУАҚЛАРИ СИНИШЛАРИ ВА ҚОН ТОМИР ЗАРАРЛАНИШИ БИЛАН ЖАБРАНГАН БЕМОРЛАГА ТИББИЙ УОДАМ ҚО'РСАТИШНИНГ МАҚБУЛ УСУЛЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, oyoq suyaklarining ochiq va yopiq sinishlarini davolash muammosi katta qon tomirlarining shikastlanishi bilan birgalikda uchragan hollarda juda dolzarb mavzudir. Bunday jarohatlarning asosiy sabablari asosan yo'l-transport hodisalari, sport jarohatlari va ishlab chiqarish bilan bog'liq jarohatlardir. Suyak sinishi paytida qon tomirlarining shikastlanishi 0,6-10% hollarda kuzatiladi, bu o'rtacha 4-5% [5, 111; 8, 58-63; 10, 308-325].

Hozirgi vaqtda angio va mikroxiirurgiyaning jadal rivojlanishi, erta o'z vaqtida tashxis qo'yish (puls oksimetriyasi, Doppler ultratovush, MSKT angiografiyasi va boshqalar) va natijada rekonstruktiv operatsiyalarni o'z vaqtida bajarish tufayli amputatsiya chastotasi sezilarli darajada kamaydi. Biroq, erishilgan yutuqlarga qaramay, amputatsiya (3-60%) va o'limning yuqori darajasi hali ham mavjud (7.3-24.0%) [2, 22-25; 7, 1011]. Masalan, bilvosita shikastlanish holatlarida, pastki uchdan bir qismidagi son sinishi 11% hollarda arteriya shikastlanishi, 8% hollarda boldir dislokatsiyasi va sonning bo'g'im ichi sinishi bilan birga keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: suyak-qon tomir shikastlanishi, to'liq va to'liq bo'lmagan amputatsiyalar, osteosintez, arterial anastomozlar, autovenoz protezlar.

Introduction. It should be noted that the problem of treating open and closed fractures of the lower extremities in combination with damage to major blood vessels is currently quite acute. The main causes of such injuries are mostly road accidents, sports injuries, and production-related injuries. Vascular damage in cases of bone fractures is observed in 0.6-10% of cases, on average accounting for 4-5% [5, 111; 8, 58-63; 10, 308-325].

Currently, with the rapid development of angio- and microsurgery, early timely diagnosis (pulse oximetry, Doppler ultrasound, MSCT angiography, etc.) and, as a result, timely reconstructive surgery, the amputation rate has significantly decreased. However, despite the achievements made, there is still a high frequency of amputations (3-60%) and fatalities (7.3-24.0%) [2, 22-25; 7, 1011]. For example, in cases of indirect trauma, a femur fracture in the lower third is accompanied by an artery injury in 11%, tibia dislocation in 8%, and intra-articular fracture of the fibula in 19% [9, 75-80].

In the workplace, injuries resulting from limbs getting caught in rotating machinery are mostly traction-crushing in nature, making them the most severe category of injuries [3, 10; 10, 312]. Particularly noteworthy are combined injuries that occur during emergencies, such as natural disasters, explosions, collapses of building structures, etc. [4, 1130; 9, 75-80]. These injuries are usually always combined and accompanied by such serious complications as severe traumatic and hemorrhagic shock, crush syndrome, asphyxia, etc.

When performing reconstructive surgery on limbs, the correct choice of osteosynthesis method, method of applying vascular anastomoses, and closure of postoperative wounds are of paramount importance.

External non-focal fixation methods using rod or rod-wire devices have clear advantages over wire fixation, as their resistance to external forces is 2.5-5 times higher [7, 1011]. External fixation may be indicated in cases of extensive soft tissue damage, wound contamination, or multi-fragment fractures [4, 1130].

Material and Methods. From 2003 to 2023, 151 patients with open and closed combined bone-vascular injuries of the lower limbs were treated in the adult and pediatric traumatology and vascular microsurgery departments of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care. There were 113 (74%) adult men, 30 (19.9%) women, and 15 (9.9%) children of both sexes under the age of 18. 127 (84.1%) patients were brought in within the first 1-6 hours after the injury, i.e., in favorable conditions for surgery. Some of the injured - 7 (4.6%) - within 6-24 hours, 17 (11.3%) - later than 1 day after the injury. 52 (34.4%) patients were self-delivered, 55 (36.4%) were delivered by ambulance, and 44 (29.1%) were transfers from other clinics. According to the mechanism of injury, patients were distributed as follows (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Distribution of patients by mechanism of injury.

As can be seen from the diagram, in most cases, 86 (57%) limb injuries were obtained as a result of road traffic accidents and often accompanied by varying degrees of traumatic brain injury. Injuries resulting from limb entrapment in rotating machinery accounted for 22%. In addition, in 20 (18.5%) cases, patients had closed abdominal and chest injuries, in 7 (4.6%) cases - pelvic fractures, and in 23 (17.2%) cases - traumatic brain injuries of varying severity. The distribution of patients by the localization of injuries is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Distribution of patients by localisation of injuries.

As can be seen from the presented diagram, the majority of injuries were localized in the area of the shin - 66 (44%) and thigh - 31 (21%). Multiple injuries (i.e., injuries to several segments) were observed in 16 (15%) patients. At admission, 115 (76.2%) patients were in a state of traumatic shock. As can be seen from the table, shock of degrees I and II predominated - 70 (60.9%), which were mainly caused by isolated bone-vascular injuries of the lower extremities. Shock of degree III was observed in 33 (28.7%) cases, more often in the presence of multiple injuries with extensive wounds of the thigh, shin, and foot.

For the purpose of analyzing treatment methods and their results, patients were divided into 4 main groups based on the nature of their injuries, as presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Division of patients into main groups.

As follows from the diagram above, 109 (72%) open fractures and dislocations with circulatory disorders were observed in the majority of the patients under consideration, which mainly

occurred in traction and crushing injuries. Complete traumatic amputations, in most cases, were also traction injuries, which were accompanied by significant damage to the severed segments. When determining the tactics and methods of treatment, we took into account the mechanism of injury, the severity of the injury and the severity of the condition at the time of admission to the hospital, as well as the nature of damage to neurovascular formations.

The main methods of investigation were clinical and laboratory, as well as radiological methods - radiography, which allowed to determine the exact localisation of the lesion. In 67 (44.4%) cases, when the patients' condition allowed, colour duplex scanning (CDS) was performed within the first hours, which allowed to determine the exact localisation of the vascular damage. MSCT-angiography was performed in 21 (13,9%) patients with closed injuries, it should be noted that stability of haemodynamic parameters of the patient was a necessary condition for this method. Pulse oximetry was performed in all patients, which allowed to establish the initial degree of segment blood circulation disturbance and the dynamics of its improvement.

Discussion of results. Group I included 8 (5.3%) patients with complete traumatic amputations of large segments. By complete amputations we meant such injuries when the connection between the injured segment and the limb was either completely absent or preserved through skin and soft tissue bridges (including those containing tendons and nerves) that did not take part in the segment blood circulation. Surgeries in this group of patients were primarily aimed at saving the patient's life. Unfortunately, due to the pronounced destruction of the segments, reconstructive surgeries were not performed in this group of patients; the surgeries consisted of primary stump formation.

Group II included 17 (11.3%) patients with incomplete traumatic amputations of large segments. In incomplete amputations in our cases, the connecting flaps contained intact veins only, which provided venous outflow from the segment. In all cases there was also nerve damage. In traction amputations, the limb was often held only on the crushed skin flaps and tendons, which had the character of the so-called subtotal amputation.

Group III included 109 (72.2%) patients with open fractures and dislocations accompanied by vascular injuries, but did not fit the category of "complete and incomplete amputations". In these cases, there was damage to musculotendinous structures, often skin and soft tissue defects, and nerve damage.

Group IV included 17 (11.3%) patients with closed fractures of long tubular bones accompanied by vascular injuries. In these cases, there was damage to a significant muscle mass, nerve injuries were practically absent or had the character of contusion.

In the last three groups, if possible, we strived to perform reconstructive surgeries. Surgical interventions were often performed against the background of traumatic shock and unstable hemodynamics, which required appropriate anesthesia, massive infusion therapy, including hemotransfusion and plasma transfusion.

When performing osteosynthesis, it was often necessary to shorten bones in order to remove non-viable fragments, as well as to facilitate reconstructive surgery on vessels and subsequent wound closure. The choice of the osteosynthesis method depended on the nature and localisation of the injury.

For fixation of bone fragments, intramedullary osteosynthesis was preferred as the least traumatic, fastest and most reliable, which saved time to a certain extent for the subsequent vascular stage of surgery. When applying vascular anastomoses, end-to-end anastomosis was used in most cases, which allowed us to reduce the time of ischemia. Bone shortening was performed to such a length that allowed to apply end-to-end vascular anastomoses, to close the wound with local tissues if possible, and not to disturb significantly the limb length.

Autovenous prosthesis was performed in the presence of significant arterial defects. In all cases, the great saphenous vein was used as a prosthesis. In the presence of traumatic arterial spasm, in the absence of effect from antispasmodics (which often occurred in traumatic shock and unstable haemodynamics), periarterial sympathectomy with dilatation with a Fogarty catheter was effective. At interposition with extravasal compression, arteriolysis was effective in the absence of signs of

arterial damage - intima rupture or complete interruption. Injuries of this nature required economical resection of the arterial ends with subsequent anastomosis. In severe combined injuries, operations on internal organs were always preceded by operations on the extremities.

In 3 (2.7%) cases due to the extremely severe condition of the patients (2 cases of road traffic accident and 1 catatrauma) the patients died in the first hours after admission.

As an illustration, here is a clinical example:

B-y: b. 1972, case history number 48466/2766

Past medical history: a fall from a height of 2 m with a fall on the left foot. The patient was brought to the Centre by an ambulance team 30 minutes later. Pre-hospital care: non-narcotic analgesics, immobilisation of the left lower limb with a Kramer splint. At treatment the patient's condition was assessed as severe, haemodynamics decreased A/D 80/40 mmHg, Pulse 110 per min. There were no peculiarities on the side of internal organs.

Fig. 1 Radiograph on admission (straight and lateral views).

Diagnosis on admission: Combined trauma. Closed splinter fracture of the lower third of the left femur with displacement of bone fragments. Damage to the left femoral artery. Ischaemia of the left lower extremity II A degree according to V.S. Savelyev. Traumatic shock of II degree.

After short-term preparation (infusion therapy) and stabilisation of haemodynamics - A/D 110/ 60 mmHg, Pulse - 100 beats per minute, the patient was transferred to the operation block by emergency indications. A sequential surgical intervention in two stages was performed:

1. open intramedullary osteosynthesis of the left femur with a pin and wire serclage.
2. Revision, resection and circular suture of the left femoral artery.

Fig. 2 Highlighting the fracture site

Fig. 3 Comparison of bone fragments

Fig 4 Stage of osteosynthesis with wire serclage.

Fig.5 Location of femoral artery injury by bone fragment

Fig.6 Circumferential suture anastomosis after resection of the lesion

Fig 7 Control radiograph after pin and wire serclage osteosynthesis.

Fig. 8 Postoperative view of the patient and SpO2 (97) on the operated limb.

The postoperative course was smooth, medication and infusion therapy were performed, the wound healed with primary tension, and the patient was discharged for outpatient treatment on 12 days. Orthopaedic regime for 6 weeks. Subsequently, the patient was activated. At the control examination 6 months later, complete consolidation of the fracture with a good anatomical-functional outcome was noted.

Out of 137 reconstructive surgeries performed in 95 (69.3%) cases, the postoperative period proceeded without complications, i.e. without recurrent circulatory failure, wound healing by primary tension, with a favourable course of the osteoreparation process. Nevertheless, the nature of the injuries and the severe general condition of the patients in 42 (30.6%) cases were the causes of various complications, including 7 (5.1%) cases that resulted in limb loss.

Postoperative complications in all cases developed within 2-7 days. Among the total number of infectious complications ($n=22$), wound suppuration with subsequent wound healing by secondary tension was noted in 17 (30.9%). In 1 (1.8%) case an anaerobic infection was noted, which entailed amputation of the segment with the subsequent wound sanitation before granulation and stump plasty with a free autotaneous graft. Arrosive bleeding due to suppuration was noted in 5 (9.1%) cases. Of the total number of thrombotic complications from anastomoses ($n=12$), reanastomosis with subsequent segment preservation was performed in 5 (10%) cases, and reamputation was performed in 7 (14%). The causes of circulatory decompensation in all cases were the development of secondary arterial thrombosis on the background of persistent unresolved peripheral spasm and deep vein thrombosis.

Fracture consolidation disorder ($n=16$) was caused by the presence of initial bone defects, impaired bone blood supply in the fracture zone, errors in osteosynthesis, and prolonged healing of postoperative wounds.

Thus, out of the total number of reconstructive surgeries performed ($n=137$), the segments were preserved in 129 (94.2%), and reamputation was performed in 8 (5.8%).

Based on the above mentioned, it can be stated that there are enough unsolved problems in the treatment of combined bone and vascular injuries of the extremities. First of all, the work of the ambulance service is still unsatisfactory. So the majority of patients according to our data - 73.7% of all patients delivered by ambulance service and transferred from other hospitals, are delivered from the places of accident, without proper medical care, in the state of traumatic and haemorrhagic shock.

In 26.5% of cases we had to deal with combined lesions, i.e., when along with injuries of the lower extremities there were closed and open craniocerebral injuries, closed injuries of the abdomen and chest. Priority in such cases was given to injuries posing a direct threat to life, while operations on the extremities were performed in the second place, which significantly increased the time interval before surgery and thus negatively affected the final result.

When choosing the tactics of surgical treatment, we proceeded first of all from the preservation of the distal limb segment and assessment of the feasibility of reconstructive surgery. In patients with fractures complicated by vascular injury, the goal of surgery was, first of all, to perform

reliable osteosynthesis and arterial anastomosis. One of the essential conditions of osteosynthesis for successful revascularisation was the shortening of the bone both in the segment and in the stump to a length sufficient for convergence of the vessel ends without tension.

Conclusion. Thus, when there is impaired blood circulation of the segment, the most optimal approach is to perform preliminary fixation (with spokes or pins) of the bone fragments necessary for revascularisation with subsequent immobilisation of the limb with external fixation apparatus after wound closure.

Nevertheless, in 14 (9.3%) cases, due to significant destruction of the damaged segments and the presence of extensive soft tissue defects, primary amputation with stump formation was performed. In another 7 (5.1%) cases, even in spite of thorough PCI and restoration of adequate blood flow in the injured segment, reamputation was performed due to the developed infectious complications. The reason for this, in our opinion, was inadequate assessment of the severity of the injury.

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